

1 **Xist controls expression of the microRNA miR-100.**

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7 We discovered control of Xist by the tumor suppressors p53 and Rb1. Non-coding RNA regulation by Xist
8 is not yet widely understood or described. We describe here control of the microRNA miR-100 by Xist. In
9 cells containing an Xist transgene, and in human embryonic pluripotent stem cells from derived from a
10 male or female, Xist expression results in miR-100 activation or is unequivocally associated with miR-100
11 expression. In mammary stem cells of the breast, Xist knockout resulted in specific activation of
12 miR100HG, as well as two separate microRNAs miR-221 and miR-222. Xist can modulate
13 transformation-related activity in cancer and likely developmental potential in health through control of
14 microRNAs like miR-100.
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